

THE IMPORTANCE OF ART IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract. Art as a part of tourism industry plays a crucial role in development of the country. Many destinations around the world are known for their art and cultural heritage, attracting tourists due to the richness and diversity of their artistic expressions. From iconic museums like the Louvre in Paris and the Museum of Modern Art in New York, to historic cities like Florence and Barcelona, art tourism draws visitors to immerse themselves in the cultural heritage and artistic legacy of these places. The aim of this article is to identify the importance of art in tourism and to suggest some ideas about developing art tourism in Uzbekistan. The paper examines one of the most popular art galleries in the world, famous artist of Uzbekistan and the prevalent methods of nurturing the growth of Uzbek artists with some advice of seasoned and renowned creative individuals. This paper demonstrates the value of art tourism and some benefits for Uzbekistan in attracting tourists to the country.

Key words: art tourism, tourism industry, art gallery, tourists, museum, artists, tourist attraction, culture, paintings, advice, tourist destination.

Аннотация. Искусство как часть индустрии туризма играет решающую роль в развитии страны. Многие туристические направления по всему миру известны своим искусством и культурным наследием, привлекая туристов богатством и разнообразием своего художественного самовыражения. От культовых музеев, таких как Лувр в Париже и Музей современного искусства в Нью-Йорке, до исторических городов, таких как Флоренция и Барселона, художественный туризм привлекает посетителей, которые хотят погрузиться в культурное и художественное наследие этих мест. Цель этой статьи - определить важность искусства в туризме и предложить некоторые идеи для развития художественного туризма в Узбекистане. В статье рассматривается одна из самых популярных художественных галерей в мире, известный узбекский художник, распространённые методы развития узбекских художников, а также несколько советов от опытных и известных творческих личностей. В этой статье демонстрируется ценность художественного туризма и некоторые преимущества Узбекистана в привлечении туристов в страну.

Ключевые слова: художественный туризм, индустрия туризма, художественная галерея, туристы, музей, художники, туристическая достопримечательность, культура, картины, советы, туристическое направление.

INTRODUCTION

Art plays a vital role in enhancing the experience of tourists and has a significant impact on the tourism industry. From historic landmarks and architectural marvels to museums and galleries, art not only enriches the cultural appeal of a destination but also contributes to its economic growth. Samarkand and some other cities in Uzbekistan are recognized as a historical city due to its ancient sights and monuments. It represents that almost no tourist comes to our country to enjoy art, whereas many countries have become famous thanks to this industry. This article aims to explore the importance of art in the tourism industry, discuss the most popular art galleries and visited countries, mention popular artists and their paintings in Uzbekistan, introduce

two experienced artists of the world and their tips for novice artists, and suggest some ideas in developing art tourism. Through a closer examination of the symbiotic relationship between art and tourism, we can better understand the pivotal role of artistic expression in shaping travel experiences and destination appeal. We will see that there is a value in art tourism and some benefits for Uzbekistan in attracting tourists to the country.

Paintings are an integral part of art tourism, as they offer a unique and immersive cultural experience for travelers. According to O'Dowd, Art tourism is a significant part of the industry as people worldwide travel to visit, discover, and participate in art festivals, concerts, wine and cuisine events, and renowned museums (2013). Art tourism refers to the travel and exploration of various cultural and artistic attractions and events across different destinations. It involves engaging in activities such as attending art festivals, concerts, and culinary events, as well as visiting popular museums and galleries to experience and appreciate different forms of art. People engage in art tourism to immerse themselves in different artistic and cultural experiences, learn about the history and traditions of the places they visit, and gain new perspectives on art and creativity. This type of tourism is a significant part of the overall tourism industry, contributing to cultural exchange, economic growth, and the promotion of art and creativity worldwide. In addition, paintings contribute to the overall aesthetic appeal of a destination and often play a significant role in shaping the identity and reputation of a city or region as an art-centric destination. Subsequently, article will examine the advanced nations in this field.

Art galleries became the tourist destination for countries such as France due to its “Louvre Museum” in Paris. According to Sfetcu (2018), “The Louvre Museum is a museum of art and antiquities located in the center of Paris in the Louvre. It is the largest of the world's art museums by its exhibition surface of 72,735 m². Its collections include nearly 460,000 works. These represent the Western art of the Middle Ages in 1848, those of the ancient civilizations that preceded and influenced it (Oriental, Egyptian, Greek, Etruscan and Roman), and the arts of early Christians and Islam” (p.2).

Figure 1. The Louvre Museum, Paris.

The prevailing prominence of the government or city can be attributed to its esteemed art gallery, renowned for its preservation of ancient artifacts, grand architectural stature, and extensive collection of culturally significant paintings. As a testament to the city's rich history and artistic legacy, the gallery serves as a magnet for tourist activity, effectively enhancing the region's economic development and tourist appeal. The sustained investment in preserving and showcasing such treasures not only reflects the city's commitment to cultural heritage but also bolsters its status as a premier tourist destination in France. Let's shift our focus to Uzbekistan, where we can explore

the art scene and the renowned artist who has brought fame to the country through his artistic contributions.

Uzbekistan is famous for its historical monuments and the country experiences lots of different ways to develop the country in tourism industry. This article's aim is to help to the country in some ways to increase tourists visit with the art tourism. It also should be noted that there are exist significant number of highly talented artists in Uzbekistan who produces captivating drawings. Regrettably, the underdeveloped nature of the state in this domain results in a lack of recognition for these artists. Despite their considerable skill and artistry, the limited infrastructure and resources for promoting and showcasing their work contribute to their relative obscurity on the global stage. This situation underscores the need for improved support and development of the arts in Uzbekistan to provide these artists with the opportunity to gain the recognition and appreciation they deserve. An example of this is Chingiz Akhmarov. According to Ummatova (2023), "Chingiz Akhmarov created a unique new art school, continuing the oriental miniature traditions and enriching them with modern styles. He was able to embody national feelings and traditions in pictures. Chingiz Akhmarov is the owner of a high talent who saturated the national traditions with oriental colors and fully expressed his unique national character in the visual art of Uzbekistan" (p.20). She claims that he was very talented artist who contributed to the history of Uzbekistan with his paintings. In addition, let's look at some advices of popular painters to beginner artists.

Figure 2. Chingiz Ahmarov, from the series "Seven Beauties"

Figure 3. Chingiz Ahmarov, from the series "Seven Beauties"

Simon Parish, born in Genoa, Italy in 1976, is a contemporary artist known for skillfully blending classical artistic traditions with his work. Drawing inspiration from the techniques of old masters, Parish showcases a profound understanding of painting's potential. His art embodies a scholarly exploration of art history while also challenging traditional conventions. Simon Parish has transitioned from utilizing oil paints on expansive canvases to producing images through the use of marker pens. Despite the conventional association of brightly colored markers with office

supplies as opposed to artistic tools, Parish adeptly employs them to communicate complex concepts through seemingly uncomplicated illustrations. His artwork has been prominently displayed throughout the United Kingdom, where he has exhibited alongside esteemed artists such as David Hockney and Lucian Freud. Parish's drawings have garnered recognition in various exhibitions, including multiple appearances in showcases organized by the prestigious Jerwood Drawing Prize. Furthermore, his talent has been acknowledged through his nomination as a finalist for the Discerning Eye Drawing Bursary.

Figure 4 A walk through the old town, Morning light, Delfino Square.

Note: In the scenes depicted by Parish, the principle of "seize the moment" prevails - "seize the moment", "live in the present". Each individual painting is a moment in time: the artist's personal observations and feelings are sublimated as eternal and unique experiences. Time stops, and life itself slows down to capture the moment.

Discussions: Inspiring Tips from Renowned Individuals for aspiring artists

One of his most inspiring tips for aspiring artists is “ The best thing an artist can have is a curiosity of the world around them. This could be an actual lived experience of the world or the world as experienced through technology or somewhere between the two. Without curiosity burning strongly it makes the process of creation all the harder. Enjoyment in what you do can really help and can be found in different areas of a practice, it’s not necessarily in the act of making, which can often just be hard work, enjoyment can often reside in the corners of processes that lead to the making of work. Don’t dismiss the slight or arbitrary thought, they can often lead to interesting possibilities.” The artist is emphasizing the importance of curiosity in the creative process. He suggests that having a strong curiosity about the world around them, whether through lived experiences or through technology, is essential for creating meaningful work. Enjoyment can be found in various aspects of the creative process, not just in the act of making art itself. The artist encourages embracing random thoughts and ideas, as they can lead to unexpected and interesting opportunities for creativity. The next one of today’s top Pop Surrealist artists is Michele Mikesell. Mikesell's work explores the universal human experience. Focusing on melding human features with anthropomorphic figures, her paintings hone in on the connectedness between human ideas and animal instinct. Irony, contradiction, humor and tragedy, are themes throughout her work. Along with the strong subject-matter, Mikesell's paintings are impeccable in their presentation. By wiping, scraping and sanding layers of paint, she builds up a surface that then given a pristine varnish, resulting in a contrasting yet uniform aesthetic. Michele’s work has been featured as one of today’s top Pop Surrealist artists, in publications like Juxtapoz Magazine, and her work characterized by playful and thought-provoking narratives. Most recently, her painting ‘Arizona Tumbleweed’ was selected for the Battersea Autumn Collection campaign! Mikesell’s work can be found internationally in many private and corporate collections, and exhibited in national and

international art fairs including, London Art Fair, AQUA Miami; SCOPE Basel, Miami and New York City; The Suite Art Fair, Dallas; Art Santa Fe; Asia Contemporary, Hong Kong and the Affordable Art Fair New York City, London, Hong Kong and Singapore.

Figure 5 *The Master of Things, Star Walker - Pop pirate portrait, Agave – beautiful cheetah woman.*

Note: Mikesell's art explores the intersection of human and animal qualities, delving into themes of irony, contradiction, humor, and tragedy. Her meticulous presentation and textured surfaces created through unique painting techniques add depth to her work, showcasing a harmonious yet contrasting visual appeal.

One of her most enlightening pieces of advice for emerging artists is “ Be honest with yourself and who you are. Don't make dishonest art. When you are ready to move on – move on. If you're not ready to move on, don't. Don't cater to what you think people want or expect from you or you will run out of fuel very quickly. Just make art. Make interesting pictures. Make what interests you. Be courageous. The world needs you right now.” The statement underscores the significance of staying authentic and producing art that is sincere and significant. It motivates artists to pursue their own interests and enthusiasms instead of conforming to external pressures. It promotes the idea of boldly expressing oneself through art without concern for external approval, as genuine creativity originates from within. The world benefits from the distinct viewpoints and creativity of every artist. In addition, let's look at some ways to develop this industry.

CONCLUSION

Art tourism can play a crucial role in the development of Uzbekistan's tourism industry. To enhance art tourism, the nation can pursue several key strategies. Firstly, investing in the promotion and recognition of local artists is paramount. Supporting talented artists such as Chingiz

Akhmarov by providing them with resources, training, and platforms to showcase their work can significantly elevate the visibility and appeal of Uzbekistan's art scene. Furthermore, establishing dedicated art districts or creative hubs within major cities, such as Tashkent, can serve as focal points for art tourism. These areas can host galleries, studios, and interactive spaces, offering tourists immersive experiences in Uzbekistan's vibrant art culture. Additionally, leveraging traditional art forms, such as Uzbek miniature painting, and integrating them with contemporary styles can create a unique artistic identity that resonates with global audiences. This fusion of tradition and modernity can serve as a compelling draw for art enthusiasts. Moreover, collaborating with international art institutions and hosting cultural exchange programs can facilitate the cross-border promotion of Uzbek art and artists. Such partnerships can raise awareness of Uzbekistan's artistic heritage and attract a diverse range of art tourists. Finally, incorporating art into tourism initiatives, such as guided art tours, art-centric events, and art-focused accommodation options, can enrich the overall visitor experience and encourage travelers to engage with Uzbekistan's artistic offerings. By implementing these measures, Uzbekistan can harness the potent allure of art tourism to heighten its appeal as a destination, attract a broader spectrum of visitors, and invigorate its tourism industry.

Art is an indispensable aspect of tourism, significantly impacting the industry by enriching cultural appeal and driving economic growth. While Samarkand is celebrated for its historical landmarks, it is often overlooked as an art destination. However, aligning art and tourism can offer valuable benefits for a destination's economy and global appeal. It is a pivotal part of the tourism industry, fostering cultural exchange and promoting creativity on a global scale. Internationally, art galleries like the Louvre Museum in Paris have made France a premier destination. The Louvre's extensive collection and historical significance draw in numerous tourists, underscoring the vital role of art in enhancing a city's appeal. In Uzbekistan, exploring the art scene and celebrated artists is essential for understanding the country's contributions to the global art landscape. Art's influence on tourism goes beyond mere aesthetics; it is an integral part of how travelers experience and interact with destinations. By recognizing the symbiotic relationship between art and tourism, destinations like Samarkand can enhance their global appeal and foster economic growth through art tourism. Art tourism allows us to travel not only to different places, but also through different cultures, histories, and perspectives.

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